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Sportsmanship Behaviors Related to Gender and Family Attitude of Secondary School Students

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Abstract

A Sportsmanship is a concept defined as the awareness of having the values required by sports and the golden key of sports activities. Family attitude and gender are thought to be among the concepts that affect sportsmanship. In this study, it was aimed to examine sportsmanship behavior with family attitude and gender characteristics. The research group consisted of 300 students randomly selected from the secondary schools in the city center of Antalya in the 2018-2019 education year, with a mean age of 12.48 ± 79 . In the research conducted with the screening model, the "Physical Education Course Sportsmanship Behavior Scale (BEDSDÖ)" developed by Koç (2013) and a personal information form were used as data collection tools. In the analysis of the data, frequency, percentage, arithmetic mean and standard deviation were used as descriptive statistics methods for personal information. As the data showed normal distribution, the t-test for paired groups and the Anova test for multiple comparisons was used. According to the findings, it was determined that the sportsmanship behaviors of the students were at a high level. A statistically significant difference was found in favor of female students in the sub-dimensions of displaying appropriate behavior according to gender and avoiding inappropriate behavior and in the total of the scale. While there was no statistically significant difference in the dimension of exhibiting appropriate behavior according to the family attitudes of the students, the scores of the students who showed democratic family attitude were higher than the scores of the children of the families with free attitudes in the dimension of avoiding inappropriate behavior and in the total of the scale. When the sportsmanship behavior scores of secondary school students were examined, it was observed that the scores of the female students were higher than the male students. It is thought that changing family attitudes will improve the sportsmanship behaviors of the society.

Keywords: Family Attitude, Gender, Sportsmanship Behavior

1. Introduction

Sport is a phenomenon that reflects the values and norms of our society. For this reason, attention should be paid to the lessons that our youth learn during sports activities. It is very important that the idea that winning fairly is

the most honorable form of victory is supported by all the participants. Therefore, sportsmanship ideals must be judged above many other aspects of the sport. Among the definitions of sportsmanship, there are elements such as playing fairly, obeying the rules of the game, respecting the decisions of the referees and officials, and treating the competitors with respect. Today, sportsmanship is defined as the "golden rule" of sports. We can demonstrate good sportsmanship by treating the people we play as we would like to be treated, and we can demonstrate sportsmanship behavior when we respect ourselves, our teammates and competitors, the coaches and referees on both sides, and other officials. But sportsmanship is not unique to people on the field. All participants, fans and parents should also be aware of how they behaved during the competition. Although physical education and play teaching programs emphasize the importance of sportsmanship in children and this combination of attitude and style may not produce the expected results without the support and assistance of parents. For this reason, the sportsmanship attitude must have an aspect that requires the support of the family together with the child. Sportsmanship is a style and demeanor and will have an impact that can be welcomed by everyone around us. Considering the developmental stages of Fleishman (1964), the process in which honesty, team spirit and group consciousness come to the fore in terms of personal and social development (Middle Childhood, 8-9 years) should be evaluated in terms of sportsmanship education. Sportsmanship should be displayed in the whole flow of life, starting from childhood games up to international encounters. However, according to the results of many researches conducted in physical education classes, it is emphasized that students are not encouraged to be sportsmanship, they do not have knowledge and experience on the concept of sportsmanship, and that students are proud even when they win by violating the principles of sportsmanship (Kaehler, 1985; Bucher, 1987). Sport, which is seen as a different area of the social society we live in together, causes an increase in the tendency to use violence and to exhibit unsportsmanlike behavior due to the increasing competitive tendencies. Unfortunately, parents and educators sometimes put too much pressure on athletes and emphasize winning at all costs. So while being a champion is great, the importance of enjoying the process of reaching the top must be emphasized. Established in 1926 to spread the principles of sportsmanship throughout life beginning from children's games up to international competitions, the International Sports Association established certain rules. These are; sticking to your teammates, keeping yourself fit, controlling your anger, keeping your game away from violence, not boasting when you win, not collapsing in a loss, being firm-spirited and open-minded for a healthy body (Keating, 2007).

For this reason, it is necessary to offer trainings that encourage sportsmanship and to identify new training models and popular opinions within sports activities. This approach should be created by considering the ethical foundations of sports.

2. Method

2.1 Model of the Research

In the research, scanning model was used. The survey model is "a research model that aims to describe a past or present situation as it is and tries to define the subject, event or object in its own conditions" (Karasar, 2008; Büyükoztürk, Kılıç-Çakmak, Akgün, Karadeniz & Demirel 2014). In this study, it was tried to determine the relationship between the sportsmanship behavior levels of secondary school students in physical education lesson with gender and family attitude values.

2.2 Population and Sampling

The population of the research consists of volunteer students who continue their education in public schools in Antalya. The sampling consists of 300 students selected from this population by random sampling method. The data were applied face to face using a questionnaire and the questions encountered during the application were answered.

2.3 Data Collection Tool

In this study, the "Physical Education Course Sportsmanship Behavior Scale (BEDSDO)" developed by Koç (2013) was used to collect data. In addition, a personal information form was used for the students to determine their gender and family attitude.

2.3.1 Physical Education Lesson Sportsmanship Behavior Scale (BEDSDO)

Physical education lesson sportsmanship behavior scale prepared for secondary school students, developed by Koç (2013) as a result of the examination of the scales and questionnaires in the literature and physical education curriculum and the opinions of the relevant students, teachers and experts is a 5-point Likert type scale.

The scale consists of 22 items and two sub-sections named "Displaying Appropriate Behaviors" (UDS) and "Avoiding Inappropriate Behaviors" (IAC). The lowest score that can be obtained from the scale is 22 and the highest score is 110. Internal consistency reliability (Cronbach Alpha) of the whole scale was calculated as 85. Increasing scores on the scale, means that students' levels of sportsmanship behavior are better (Koç, 2013).

2.4 Data Analysis

In the analysis of the data, frequency, percentage, arithmetic mean and standard deviation were used as descriptive statistics methods for personal information. As the data showed normal distribution, t-test in paired groups and ANOVA test in multiple comparisons were used.

3. Findings

Table 1: Descriptive statistics for students' personal data

Variability		N	%
Gender	Female	147	49,0
	Male	153	51,0
Class	Class 6	37	12,3
	Class 7	205	68,3
	Class 8	58	19,4
Family Attitude	Domineering	28	9,3
	Demokratik	228	76,0
	Free	44	14,7
License	License available	60	16,7
	License n/a	240	83,3

Looking at Table 1, it is seen that 49 % of the students are female (n = 147) and 51% are male (n = 153). 12.3 % of these students are 6th class (n = 37), 68.3 % of them are Class 7 (n = 205), 19.4 % of them are class 8 (n = 58) secondary school students. 16.7 % of the students participating in the study were licensed sports students (60), and 83.3% were students who did not have a license (n = 240).

Table 2: Min, max values and average of BEDSDO scores of secondary school students

Scale	N	Min	Max	X	SS
Displaying appropriate behavior	300	2,50	5,00	4,12	,66
Refrain from inappropriate behavior		1,00	5,00	4,30	,77
BEDSDÖ		2,36	5,00	4,21	,59

Table 2 shows that the average scores of the candidates exhibiting appropriate behavior in the alternative sub-dimension of the scale are the highest ($\bar{x}$ item = 4.12), then avoiding appropriate behavior ($\bar{x}$ item = 4.30) and the scale total ($\bar{x}$ item = 4), , 21). It can be said that the sportsmanship behavior of the candidates is good and at a

high score level. In the study, a t-test was conducted to determine the change of sportsmanship behavior levels according to gender and, the results are presented in Table 3.

Table 3: Comparison of Students' Scale Scores According to Gender (t-test results)

Scale	Gender	N	X	SS	t	p
Displaying appropriate behavior	Female	147	4,20	,62	2,015*	,045
	Male	153	4,04	,69		
Refrain from inappropriate behavior	Female	147	4,58	,51	6,893*	,000
	Male	153	4,02	,83		
BEDSDO	Female	147	4,39	,47	5,571*	,000
	Male	153	4,03	,64		

p<0.05

Table 3 shows a statistically significant difference in the appropriate behavior of the subjects according to their gender (t = 2.015, p = .045), and a statistically significant difference was determined in refraining inappropriate behavior (t = 6.893 p = .000) and physical education lesson sportsmanship scale (t = 5.571, p = ,000). The average point of sportsmanship behavior of female students is higher than that of male'. Anova results regarding the physical education course sportsmanship behavior scale scores of secondary school students according to their family attitudes are given in Table 4.

Table 4: Comparison of Students' Scale Scores according to Family Attitudes (Anova results)

Scale	Attitude	N	X	SS	F	P	Difference
Displaying appropriate behavior	1- Domineering	28	3,99	,70	1,344	,262	
	2- Democratic	228	4,15	,62			
	3-Free	44	4,01	,84			
Refrain from inappropriate behavior	1- Domineering	28	4,22	,70	6,276*	,002	2-3
	2- Democratic	228	4,37	,71			
	3- Free	44	3,94	1,00			
Scale Total	1- Domineering	28	4,11	,57	4,938*	,008	2-3
	2- Democratic	228	4,26	,55			
	3- Free	44	3,98	,76			

p<0.05

No significant difference was noted in displaying appropriate behavior from sportsmanship behaviors of secondary school students according to their family attitudes (F = 1,344, P = ,262) but according to the free family attitude of the democratic family attitude, there is a significant difference in refraining inappropriate behavior (F = 6,276, P = ,002) as presented in Table 4. When the democratic family attitude was compared with the free family attitude, a statistically significant difference was found (F = 4.938, P = .008) in the total scale.

4. Discussion

According to the results obtained in the study conducted with the aim of examining the sportsmanship behaviors of secondary school students in physical education lesson in terms of gender and family attitude variables, it can be said that the total scores of the sportsmanship behavior scale in physical education classes are high. Similar to the findings of the study, Altun and Güvendi (2019) reported that secondary school students display sportsmanship behaviors of students considering the general average results of sportsmanship behaviors in physical education classes (Altun & Güvendi, 2019). Unlike our research findings, Karafil et al. (2017) stated that, the sportsmanship scores of the students in a study they conducted with middle school students aged 10-15 as medium is in average level (Karanfil, Altay, Ulaş & Melek, 2017).

When the sportsmanship behavior of the students was examined according to the gender variable, a statistically significant difference was found in favor of female students in displaying appropriate behavior, refraining

inappropriate behavior and in the total of the scale. The findings obtained in the study are in parallel with the findings of the literature (Ekinici & Koç, 2020; Gürpınar, 2014). Turkmen and Varol (2015), in their study with secondary school students reported that, female students have higher levels of sportsmanship compared to male students and that female students avoid unsportsmanlike behaviors (Türkmen & Varol, 2015). Altun and Güvendi (2019), in their study with middle school students reported that, according to gender variable, the total scores of sportsmanship of female students were significantly higher than the scores of male students. Certel et al. (2020), in their research with middle school students found that, female students' mean scores for sportsmanship behavior were higher than male students. Similarly, Esentürk et al. (2015) and Tsai and Fung (2005) reported in their study that the total scores of the sportsmanship behavior scale in physical education lesson of female students were higher than that of male students. Differing from the research findings, there are also studies reporting that male students' sportsmanship behavior scale scores are higher than female students (Karanfil et al., 2017; Dorak, 2015; Kayışoğlu, Altınkök, Temel & Yüksel, 2015).

In addition, there are studies reporting that male and female students get similar scale scores according to the gender variable (Hacıcaferoğlu, Selçuk, Hacıcaferoğlu & Karataş, 2015). Unlike our research findings, when the sportsmanship behavior of students is examined according to gender variable, it is seen that there are studies that do not find a statistically significant difference (Miller, Roberts & Ommundsen, 2004; Shields, La Voi, Bredemeier & Power, 2007).

While there was no statistically significant difference in the dimension of students exhibiting appropriate behavior according to their family attitudes, in the dimension of refraining inappropriate behavior and in the total of the scale, the scores of the students showing democratic family attitude were higher than the scores of the children of families with free attitudes in the study. Similar to the findings of our research, Certel et al. (2020), in their research with middle school students reported that children of families with a democratic family attitude had higher mean scores for refraining inappropriate behavior and sportsmanship than students with a free family attitude. The concept of sportsmanship contains many meanings. Sportsmanship helps to make all competitive games fun and enjoyable. It enables to be a good sportsperson and develops good habits and positive life skills inside and outside sports games. It should be taken into consideration that sportsmanship is more than just being kind to others. There are several essential qualities that contribute to athlete behavior. These are; to be supportive; If you are losing, it is best not to exploit your frustration on your teammates. Being a team player requires showing support to other teammates. In a game, all of the players strive for performing their best and to win. In such situations, positive reinforcement also plays a key role that leads higher productivity. A few words of encouragement or a clap can sometimes be all a person needs to get their thought back into the game. Maintaining a positive attitude. Having a negative attitude to the game can lead the whole team down. This may result in less enjoyable tournament for everyone. Positivity is an essential feature, particularly while playing team sports. Moreover, the match result regarding winning or losing is better not to affect any behavior like being disrespectful to both teammates and opponent players. Sportsmanship requires avoiding being aggressive or insulting the opponent teams during or after the game. Whining about calls or arguing with the referees, can also be considered as unsportsmanlike behavior. Inspiring the spirit of the game and desiring to learn are great ways to attain a sportsmanship. For athletes showing sportsmanship behavior, learning from their mistakes is preferred approach instead of thinking about revenge from the opponents. For example, if you push too hard during a tennis match and make a mistake, practice "spinning the balls back" that has you the most challenge. To practice self-regulation. Moreover, games may be emotional yet, players are better to make a conscious effort to control their emotions and focus on the game. Damaging sports equipment is not a proper behavior considering an athlete with sportsmanship (<https://www.masterclass.com/> Date of access, 25.03.2021).

Good sportsmanship is essential since it makes competitive play more favourable and fun for each player. Bad sportsmanship creates a negative climate and can take fun out of the game. For this reason, it is necessary to offer trainings that encourage sportsmanship and to identify new training models and popular opinions within sports activities. This approach should be created by considering the ethical foundations of sports.

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